

SHEIKH NURIDDIN BASIR**Mirzayev Nuriddin Fakhriddinovich**

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Annotation: Among many historical monuments, this monument also served to bring down very important information from the distant sixties to us. Meanwhile, it is our priority to bring this divine abode to the next generation by drawing public attention to it.

Key words: Mausoleum, mosque, distant history, Great Silk Road, Timurid period, Movoraunnahr, historical battles, Russian invasion, historical records.

Not far from the Hazrat Khizr Mosque, behind the world-famous Shahi-Zinda memorial complex, on the southern edge of the ancient Afrasiab settlement, next to a spring with clear water, there is a remarkably modest mausoleum of Sheikh Nuriddin Basir. Once upon a time, the owner A. Temur himself got off his horse to pray at this man's grave, and although pious people took off their shoes when passing by the saint's tomb, not all Samarkand residents, even visitors to the city, know about him. Who was Nuriddin Basir and why Sahibqiran respected him.

This breed was originally from Nuzhkent (a village near Tashkent region) and was trained by the famous sheikh Zayniddin Sukhrovardi (who lived in the second half of the 13th century) who lived in the Lower Orifon region near Tashkent. When Nuriddin Basir reached the status of sheikh, he moved to Samarkand at the invitation of his elder, settled in Masjid Kabud (Blue Mosque) located on the banks of the Navodon spring, and served as sheikh. He followed the path of "jahriya" in the tariqat, that is, chanting. From a young age, his mother was born crippled and received the nickname "Basir". Under the tutelage of his murshid Sheikh Zainiddin, he rose to the

rank of a saint and reached a high status. He was asked, "Who are the Qutb (saintly authors) in your time?" When they asked him, he answered: "My brother Abdullah is the thirteenth pole, and I am the fourteenth," and that is why he is known as "Qutbi Chordahum" among the people. Nuriddin Basir, successor of Sukhrovardiya's teachings, dies in 1242. According to his will, the sheikh will be buried near the Navodon spring.

About two and a half centuries later, Amir Temur, who became the ruler of a huge kingdom, decided to move Nuriddin Basir's ashes to the Koksaroy fortress with the advice of his spiritual mentors (probably Burkhanuddin Sagarji) and built a majestic mausoleum with a dome over the grave. The height of the dome reached five meters and it was visible from all points of Samarkand.

Many buildings were erected in the gorge where Amir Temur's troops were located. Among them, the most famous are the Cosmic Swing, Cox's Palace and Boston Palace. Timur often visited Nuriddin Basir's mausoleum before important campaigns and offered prayers.

After some time, Burkhanuddin Sagarji, the head of Beijing Muslims, bequeathed to bury himself near the Basir mausoleum, and the Rukhabad mausoleum was built on top of his ashes. In general, in the middle of the 14th century, Basir was revered in Samarkand to such an extent that, according to historian Abdul Hasan, pious people and religious figures, including Sheikh ul-Islam, walked by his grave and even took off their shoes.

Thus, another reason for the glorification of Nuriddin Basir is that Sheikh Shamsiddin Kulol, who was his spiritual teacher in his youth, had a great influence on the religious views of Amir Temur. It is recognized that it was he who inspired the young

Temur to have a high destiny as a future ruler. Sheikh Kulol lived in the cities of Karshi and Kesh for a long time and gained an incomparable spiritual reputation in Barlos.

During the Hajj to Makkah, Kulol joins the Suhrowardiya order in the Sufi centers of Iraq and begins to spread this teaching in Movoraunnahr. We remind you that Sheikh Nuriddin Basir, who lived a hundred years before Kulol, also belonged to the Suhurwardiya sect. By the way, the influence of this Sufism on Amir Temur is also evidenced by the fact that it was built on the mausoleum of Sheikh Basir's mentor, Sheikh Zaynaddin Kuyi Orifon (Grandfather Zaynaddin) in Tashkent.

Unfortunately, the fate of the Nuriddin Basir mausoleum built by Temur was sad, and after Samarkand was conquered by the Russian Empire in 1868, a defensive fortress was built on Koksaroy Hill. According to historical data, the ruins of the Koksaroy and Bostonsaroy palaces, Nuriddin Basir's mausoleum and other buildings of the Temur era were completed in the territory of the Russian fortress. In those days, the demolition of buildings, especially the demolition of the prestigious mausoleum, caused a strong protest of the people of Samarkand, and the then chief judge of Samarkand, Said Mir Nizamiddin Khoja (descendant of Makhdumi Azam), with the permission of the authorities, moved the relics of the holy sheikh to the territory of the Hazrat Khizr Mosque, until now. on the ground.

During the Soviet era, the grave of the saint was forgotten and abandoned. But after Uzbekistan gained independence in 1991, scientists organized historical documents and determined the exact location of Nuriddin Basir's grave, and in 1997, the descendants of Said Mir Nizamiddin Khoja built the present mausoleum over the saint's grave thanks to voluntary donations from the people of the city. A picture of a majestic mausoleum from the 14th century hangs here to this day as a reminder of Samarkand's losses.

In conclusion, today those who visit the historical monument where the graves of our Sheikh are located can find cures for many diseases by drinking from the spring water located next to it, and if they go around the tomb three or seven times and sincerely ask for their wishes, it is history and today found his proof.

Sources

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